

CONSTRUCTIVIST APPROACH IN ENGLISH SUBJECT TO DEVELOP LISTENING SKILL OF SCHOOL STUDENTS

Mr. Vilas Vitthal Bhise

Research Scholar ,

University Of Mumbai

Research Guide: Dr. Sunayana J. Kadle

Abstract

“Language and culture are the frameworks through which humans experience, communicate, and understand reality.”

Lev Vygotsky

English has been started from first standard in Marathi medium schools also from June 2000. The goal of teaching English from first standard is with the objective that the students will attain knowledge proficiency and will be able to communicate well as it is one of the main communication language of the multilingual society But unfortunately, even after a decade, the desired goals have not been achieved to the full extent. Teachers generally used direct approach of starting the class making use of textbooks. The teachers have fallen into ‘the Textbook Trap.’ They use the textbook as their primary instructional tool in all the classrooms and adhered only to the written word and printed instructions. There is less effort to move beyond the textbooks. Language is best learnt through the development of four skills. The skills of speaking, listening, reading and writing. It is seen that teachers consider skill development as an integrated practice; integrated in the sense that they feel listening and speaking automatically learnt during reading and writing. Listening and speaking do not require separate exercises, games or activities, but can be learnt while practicing reading skills by reading aloud. There is a need for teachers to shift focus of teaching from Traditional method to new approaches so as to make the teaching learning process more effective, attractive, and joyful and child centered. One such approach is the constructivist approach. In this scenario the researcher took up an experimental research in constructivist learning in English subject. In the present paper researcher shared his experiences of using constructivist approach in English subject for

developing the listening skill. The instructional units based on 7 'E' s of constructivism were developed and its effectiveness was studied on the 40 students from Navi Mumbai Municipal School No 30 Kopri Vashi. It was found that the students enjoyed the learning process and developed their listening skills. One such plan has been presented in this paper.

Key words: *English subject Instructional units, constructivist approach, Listening skill*

Introduction:

“Language and culture are the frameworks through which humans experience, communicate, and understand reality.”

Lev Vygotsky

In the world many languages are spoken in different countries, states, cultures such as English, French, German, Spanish, Hindi, Marathi etc. among them English is mostly used in many countries so English is an international language. We can converse with a person with each other in any language, but if we have to converse with a person from another country, then we cannot speak in a regional language. English is the language widely used for communication. Besides this, the world is coming closer because of technology. Information on various topics is available on in English language. To accumulate more knowledge it becomes necessary to learn English.

By understanding importance of English, Government of Maharashtra started English subject in the syllabus from the 1st standard from year 2000 in vernacular medium schools. There are many schools which are known as semi English Medium where in mathematics and science are taught in English due to which the students have to learn English language. In spite of this many students from Marathi medium schools cannot speak English. They cannot express themselves and communicate well in English. If we look into results of Std.10th maximum students fail in English subject. They cannot go for further studies due to this failure.

One reason for this failure is fear about English. Due to this fear students do not speak English. Second reason is the lack of confidence. This fear and lack of confidence is because the children have not learnt the subject properly. One of the reasons may be the teaching methods used in schools. In many schools teachers used traditional methods for teaching where in focus is on reading the text and explaining vocabulary and that too the English is taught in the mother tongue means the sentences of the text are explained in the language which children understand or medium of school. Therefore students cannot

learn English subject properly. They do not like to learn English also cannot speak English fluently. There is a need for teachers to shift focus of teaching from Traditional method to new approaches so as to make the teaching learning process more effective, attractive, and joyful and child centered. One such approach is the constructivist approach.

Constructivist approach is a teaching and learning process that has been proved to have a lasting impact on both curriculum and instructions. In a traditional curriculum a teacher transmits information to students who passively listen and acquire facts. But in a constructivist curriculum and instructional design, students are actively involved in their learning to reach new understanding. Constructivism based instructional design foster critical thinking and creates active and motivated learners and they made up their mind to invent and construct new ideas.

Seven E's Instructional Model of Constructivism:-

Each of the 7 E's describes a phase of learning, and each phase begins with the letter "E": Elicit, Engage, Explore, Explain, and Elaborate. Evaluate and Extend the 7 E's allows students and teachers to experience common activities, to use and build on prior knowledge and experience, to construct meaning, and to continually assess their understanding of a concept.

7E Instructional model is a series of seven planned and interconnected phases in which the learner goes through various scientific investigations by exploring teaching material, build the concept after arriving at a certain conclusion and finally apply the concept or a principle in a novice situation. The description of each phase of the 7E model is given as under:

- 1. Elicit:** This phase activates the student's existing knowledge.
- 2. Engage:** In this phase the students are engaged in the activity and instructions are given
- 3. Explore:** In this phase the students are given various opportunities to think freely but within the limits of the activities.
- 4. Explain:** In this phase students are given opportunities to verbalize their conceptual understandings.
- 5. Elaborate:** This phase helps in extending learner's conceptual understanding. Students will get deeper understanding of the concepts by performing similar kinds of activities

6. Evaluate: In this phase teacher will assess student's understanding of the concept with formative as well as summative evaluation.

7. Extend: In this phase students tend to apply the skill or a principle learned in the classroom in a new situation.

Need of the Study

The researcher is an English teacher for past 20 years. The researcher has observed that the students are unable to apply the gained knowledge about English in day to day life. They are unable to express themselves and communicate fluently. The researcher while going through literature has come across the constructivist approach to teach different subjects and the literature showed that it's a student centered and successful method for teaching different subjects so the following Research Questions came to the researchers mind.

1. Can constructivist approach be used for teaching English?

The researcher felt induced to seek answer to the question:

Statement of Problem:

“Impact of instructional units in English subject based on constructivist approach on development of listening skill of students studying in of Marathi medium school.”

Objectives:

- To develop instructional units in English of listening skill for STD VII students of Marathi medium schools based on constructivist approach.
- To study the impact of instructional units in English of listening skills of school students.

Hypothesis:

- There is no significant difference in the listening skill of the students taught by using the instructional units in English of listening skill reflected in their scores before and after treatment. (Pre test -Post test)

Methodology And Procedure

The present study is a developmental research as well as an experimental research. The Research Methodology of the present study consists of **two parts**:

- 1. Development of lessons in English subject on listening skill for std VII using constructivist approach.**
- 2. Study of the effect of instructional units in English subject of listening skill based on constructivist approach on students of std. VII**

The following research designs was used to study the effectiveness of instructional units in English subject of listening skill based on constructivist approach. The total sample was 40 students of the seventh standard belonging to N.M.M.C.School No 30 Kopri the SSC Board.

Pretest Post test One Group Design

Pretest (X) → (treatment) → 01 Post Test(X)

R Treatment - Lessons conducted by using 7E strategies by the researcher for the X (Experimental) group .

The researcher taught the students using the instructional unit in English subject on listening skill based on constructivist approach.

Before the start of the treatment, a pre-test based on the listening skill was administered and the planned lessons were implemented. After which the post test was administered and the effectiveness based on the scores obtained on the tests were analysed.

Analysis Of The Data:

The data was subjected to descriptive and inferential analysis.

Descriptive Analysis :

The means of the scores on the pre test and post test were computed .

Pre-test	40	10.47
Post test	40	15.75

Findings:-

The means of the scores on the post test is greater than that on the pretest .This means that the students have gained in their listening skill.

Testing of the Hypothesis

- There is no significant difference in the listening skill of the students taught by using the instructional units in English of listening skill reflected in their scores before and after treatment. (Pre test -Post test)

Group	N	Mean	σ	σ_m	df	t
Pre-test	40	10.47	10	3.88	39	1.90**
Post test	40	15.75	16			

** P <.01, * P <.05

The calculated 't' value (1.90) is significant at 0.01 level of significance.

This implies that the instructional units in English subject of listening skill based on constructivist approach were effective in increasing the listening skill of the students of the experimental group. The null hypothesis is rejected.

Suggestions and Educational Implications:

The Present study has made an attempt to develop listening skill of English of the students in the school using the constructivist approach for teaching English. These strategies were found to be very effective in developing the listening skill of the students while teaching the curricular subject English without spending extra time.

Teachers can implement such newer strategies or methods and students also will be exposed to new strategies and a lot of interaction will be developed in the classroom among the students. This will give scope for students to think, interact, help each other and understand each other's feelings and difficulties. This benefits them in all aspects.

Lesson Plan Sample

LESSON PLAN FOR LISTENING SKILL -01

Class: English 7th

Teacher: VILAS BHISE

Target Audience: Primary

Students Number: 40

Name of the Topic: Conversations with subtitles.

Skill: Listening

Grammar Focus: “WH” Questions

Duration: 60 minutes

Content of Topic:

This lesson plan is about listening skill. Teacher tell students they are going to hear a conversation between man and woman Teacher play an Audio Video clip On the you tube. <https://youtu.be/RQPSzkMNwew> .

I. Objectives/Learning Outcomes

- To develop listening skill.
- To develop the skill of framing ‘WH’ questions.
- To work cooperatively to collaborate on a related activity.

II. Prior Knowledge

- Students listen various conversations in school
- Students knows the words starts from “WH” alphabets.

III. Materials

- Audio clip
- Work sheet

Class arrangement: Students will be made to sit in pairs.

TEACHING AND LEARNING ACTIVITIES	
Teacher Activity	Student Activity
<p>ELICIT</p> <p>Teacher will introduce the lesson by asking students the following questions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Raju when will you get the story book?• Smita what is the color of your bag?• Meena where is your pen?• Which sense organ did you use so that you could answer me? <p>Teacher will say that since you have answered to my questions by listening to me today we will learn about WH questions</p> <p>The name of the topic will be written on the board</p>	<p>Students will respond to the questions asked by the teacher</p>

<p>ENGAGE</p> <p>Teacher tells the students that they will be doing an interesting activity.</p> <p>Teacher tells the students they are going to hear conversation between man and woman. The following instructions will be given:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Put your pens down• Listen first.• After the listening activity is over Individually make any jottings if required• discuss with the partner about the contents of the audio clip <p>The audio record will be played by the teacher</p>	<p>Students will listen and follow the instructions of the teacher.</p>
<p>EXPLORE</p> <p>Teacher will play the audio clip https://youtu.be/rqpszkmnwcw and observe the students and maintain the discipline in the class</p> <p>Teacher will go around and help if required</p>	<p>Students will observe the clip and then write down the names they have heard in the clip and perform as per the instructions</p> <p>Students will first write the names individually and then they will pair up with the partner and discuss on what they heard in audio.</p>
<p>EXPLAIN</p> <p>Teacher will conduct open discussion. Teacher will observe the students Discussion will be done on following questions.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Where is Jane?2. Where are Bill and Mary?3. Where is the dog?4. Where is School?	<p>Each of the students pair will present in front of the class what they have listened</p>

<p>5.What is your favorite colour?</p> <p>Each pair is required to present their oral presentation to the whole class. Each pair has to orally introduce and discuss briefly the character and theme of the audio. In addition, the presentation needs to include a discussion about the audio, situation or event that is being portrayed in the audio clip</p>	
<p>ELABORATE</p> <p>Teacher will explain students in depth about “WH” questions and will proceed with playing the audio once again.</p>	<p>Students will listen attentively</p>
<p>EVALUATE</p> <p>Teacher will ask each of the students to write 10 “WH” questions. Teacher will provide feedback when they are presenting to class and will assist students who have problems in order to get this task done time and effectively.</p>	<p>The students will do the task</p>
<p>EXTEND</p> <p>Teacher will Ask the student to listen to conversations between two people at home and then write what all wh questions are being asked during conversations</p>	<p>Students will make note of the Home assignment it in their books.</p> <p>They will work towards it at home.</p>

References:

Creswell, J. W.(2002)

Educational Research, Planning, Conducting and Evaluating Quantitativ and Qualitative Research, University of Netvaska, Merill Prentice hall,

Best, J. W. and Kahn, J. V, (2003)

Research in Education.(9thed). New Delhi: Prentic Hall of India Pvt. Ltd.

Dandekar, W. N, (1986)

Evaluation in Schools. Poona: ShrividyaPrakashan

Brooks,J.G.andBrooks,M.G.(1993)

Alexandria,VA:Association for supervision and Curriculum Development

Piaget.J.(1936,1977)

The origin of intelligence in child.Penguin Education,Middlesex.England

Websites:

<http://constructivism/caldigestlanguage-teaching-methodology.htm>

[http://learning theory of instructional design.htm](http://learning-theory-of-instructional-design.htm)

[http://constructivism\constructivism.htm](http://constructivism/constructivism.htm)

[http://constructivism\what is intercultural english teaching.htm](http://constructivism/what-is-intercultural-english-teaching.htm)

[http://www.funderstanding.com\constructivism.cfm](http://www.funderstanding.com/constructivism.cfm)